

Thermodynamic Parameters of Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) Chelates with Glutamic Acid

R. C. AGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, Bipin Bihari College, Jhansi-284 001

Manuscript received 30 August 1976, revised 30 March 1977, accepted 3 October 1977.

The thermodynamic parameters of Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) chelates with glutamic acid were determined potentiometrically in aqueous solution at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in an ionic strength of 0.1 M KCl. The stability constant ($\log K$), change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complexes are reported. The increase in the values of stability constants of rare-earth metal ions with increase in atomic number are explained on the basis of lanthanide contraction.

AMINO acids play a greater role, as many of them are essential for human life. The complexes of several aminoacids with transition metal ions having incomplete d-subshell or f-subshell are reported in literature. Recently the author and his coworkers¹ have studied the interaction of La(III) and Ce(III) with glutamic acid in solution state by potentiometric titration technique. In continuation to the above studies the author now has taken to study the interaction of Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) with glutamic acid in the solution state. In this paper the stability constants, overall change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) with glutamic acid at two different temperatures $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$ are reported. In this communication an attempt is also made to establish and confirm the relationship between the rare-earth metal ions i.e. La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) etc.

Experimental

The nitrate salts of Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) were dissolved in conductivity water. The metal content of the solutions were gravimetrically estimated by precipitating the metal as metal oxalate and then ignited as metal oxide^{1,2}. Standard carbonate free NaOH was used for potentiometric titrations. The glutamic acid used was in the form of mono-sodium glutamate. All the chemicals used were Anal-R (B.D.H. or equivalent).

The experimental procedure involved a series of pH-titrations of glutamic acid with standard NaOH solution in the absence and presence of metal ions at 30° and 40° in a constant temperature water-bath where the temperature was electrically controlled with in 0.1° . In all the titrations, volume (50 ml.) and ionic strength (0.1 M KCl) were kept constant. Other experimental details were already explained by the author in previous papers^{3,4}.

Results and Discussions

At different pH, the horizontal distances between the curves in absence and presence of metal ions, measure quite accurately the additional base consumed due to complex formation, i.e.,

(Where M^{3+} denotes rare-earth metals and NaG.H denotes mono-sodium glutamate).

Therefore at various pH, the different \bar{n} and $\log \left(\frac{1}{A} \right)$ i.e., $\log K$ values were obtained for each metal at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by integral method of Calvin-Bjerrum^{5,6,7} as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁸. The different \bar{n} and $\log K$ values so obtained were plotted and metal-ligand stability constants were read directly from graphs at $\bar{n}=0.5$ for 1 : 1, metal-ligand ratio. The ratio of metal-ligand interaction was also determined by conductometric titration as adopted by Job⁹.

The metal-ligand stability constant of rare-earth metal ions with glutamic acid and thermodynamic parameters i.e., change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) are reported in the table.

On going through the values of different constants for La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) from author's another paper¹ and the table it is evident that the order of stability constants follow the well established order i.e.,

The above mentioned elements have partly filled f-subshells and therefore they are also known as inner transition metals. Since the f-orbitals are deep

AGARWAL : THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF PR(III), ND(III) AND SM(III) ETC.

TABLE-1 METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES AT $\mu = 0.1\text{KCl}$.

		30±0.1°	40±0.1°
Metal Ligand Stability Constant log K	Pr(III)	3.855	3.702
	Nd(III)	3.956	3.814
	Sm(III)	4.087	3.955
Change in free energy (ΔG) in KCal./Mole.	Pr(III)	-5.346	-5.303
	Nd(III)	-5.475	-5.449
	Sm(III)	-5.667	-5.635
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in KCal./Mole.	Pr(III)	-6.639	For the difference of 10°
	Nd(III)	-6.162	
	Sm(III)	-5.772	
Change in entropy (ΔS) in Cal/degree/Mole.	Pr(III)	-4.268	-4.269
	Nd(III)	-2.268	-2.237
	Sm(III)	-0.345	-0.438

seated and all the f-electrons have the same radial distribution, addition of electrons cannot change the size of the elements distinctly. Therefore in these inner transition metals (lanthanides) the difference in the values of stability constant, if any, is mainly due to *lanthanide contraction*. Similar types of behaviour for lanthanide complexes were also observed by several other investigators with different other complexing agents ¹⁰⁻¹³.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to M/s. Indian Rare Earths Ltd., Udyogmandal (Kerala) for supply of rare-earth salts as free samples and Dr. B.S. Rajput, Govt. College, Datia for necessary suggestions.

References

1. R. C. AGARWAL, R. P. KHANDELWAL and P. C. SINGHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (In press).
2. R. C. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 772.
3. R. C. AGARWAL and R. P. KHANDELWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (In press)
4. R. C. AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 727.
5. M. CALVIN & K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
6. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3270.
7. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution". P. HASSE and SON, COPENHAGEN, 1941.
8. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904 ; 1953, 3397.
9. P. JOB, *Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 204 ; 1925, 180, 928 ; 1922, 176, 422.
10. G. SCHWARZENBACH, R. GUT and G. ANDEREGG, *Helv. Chem. Acta.*, 1954, 37, 937.
11. R. HARDER and S. CHABERK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1959, 11, 197.
12. B. MAITI, N. MAHADEVAN and R. M. SATHE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 1152.
13. S. L. PANIA, K. N. KAUL & R. K. MEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 972.